

Deliverable 6.6

Events

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Document History and Information

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1. Introduction

The objectives of the Events deliverable is to provide a list of significant events (conferences, seminars, workshops) which will represent dissemination and outreach opportunities for RETHINK project partners. This deliverable will be updated in M12 and M24.

During the months of February and March 2019, all project partners have had the opportunity to provide a list of events, workshops, seminars, etc. where they will be talking about / showcasing RETHINK. The full list is provided in the following pages.

2. Events

2.1 STICHTING VU

Name of the event: Staff convent

Location: Athena Institute (VU), Amsterdam

Dates: 5th of February, 2019.

Target audience: Athena's employees

Potential number of participants: Around 30 participants

How will you present RETHINK there? Presentation on the RETHINK project

Name of the event: Vakconferentie Wetenschapscommunicatie 2019

Location: Amsterdam

Dates: 15th of April, 2019

Target audience: Science communication practitioners

Potential number of participants: 70-80 participants

How will you present RETHINK there? Short presentation + world café setting

2.2 Ecsite

Name of the event: Ecsite annual conference 2019

Location: Experimentarium, Copenhagen, Denmark

Dates: 6-8 June 2019

Target audience: Science engagement practitioners, museum professionals, science communicators

Potential number of participants: Around 1.100

How will you present RETHINK there? Flyers

2.3 UWE Bristol

Name of the event: Science in Public Conference

Location: Manchester Metropolitan University

Dates: 10-12 July 2019

Target audience: Science communication researchers and practitioners

Potential number of participants: Unknown

How will you present RETHINK there? Panel discussion

Name of the event: PARI Conference

Location: Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Oxford

Dates: 8-10 April, 2019

Target audience: Science Communication Professionals, Public relations staff for research organisations

Potential number of participants: Unknown

How will you present RETHINK there? Oral presentation on the scoping study.

RETHINK D6.6

Name of the event: South West Science Communication Conference

Location: TBC

Dates: 21 June 2019

Target audience: Science Communication Professionals and academics

Potential number of participants: Unknown

How will you present RETHINK there? Oral presentation.

2.4 ZU

Name of the event: German Week in St. Petersburg, Russia (this year's topic: Research and Universities, organized by the German consulate and the Goethe Institute, partnering organization ITMO university)

Location: St. Petersburg

Dates: 05.-06.04.2019

Target audience: Students, academics, interested lay people

Potential number of participants: Unknown

How will you present RETHINK there? Oral presentation referring to questions of Science communication education in the context of a course offered at ITMO university and in the context of a panel discussion on universities' third mission at the German Week

Name of the event: International communication Association, annual conference, Washington D.C.

Location: Washington, D.C., USA

Dates: 23. -28.05.2019

Target audience: Communication scholars

Potential number of participants: Unknown

How will you present RETHINK there? Oral presentation

2.5 SML

Name of the event: European Week of Regions and Cities

Location: Brussels (Belgium)

Dates: 7-10 October 2019

Target audience: Policy makers, researchers, journalists

Potential number of participants: 6.000

How will you present RETHINK there? Flyer

Name of the event: Stati Generali della Ricerca e dell'Innovazione 2019

Location: Milan (Italy)

Dates: 24-25 June 2019

Target audience: Policy makers, researchers, journalists

Potential number of participants: 300

How will you present RETHINK there? Flyer

RETHINK D6.6

Name of the event: EUSEA Annual Conference 2019

Location: Vienna (Austria)

Dates: 9-10 May 2019

Target audience: Science communication practitioners, mediators, science festivals

Potential number of participants: 400

How will you present RETHINK there? Flyer

Name of the event: Pathways to Transformation Conference, Nucleus and RRI-practice projects 2019

Location: Brussels (Belgium)

Dates: 20-21 June 2019

Target audience: Science communication practitioners, researchers, policy makers

Potential number of participants: 200

How will you present RETHINK there? Flyer

2.6 DBT

DBT's own Work Package (WP5) will be active M25-M36. At this moment, M3, DBT has no confirmed dissemination events for 2019.

